

What Kinds of Geography Test Questions Generate Controversy? A Qualitative Analysis of 83 Videos from a Chinese Social Media Platform

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Abstract

This qualitative study analyzes 83 commentary videos posted by a Chinese social media account between March 2018 and January 2024, focusing on disputed geography questions from China's National College Entrance Examination (Gaokao). Employing a process of 'text organization - coding classification - system construction', the video content was analyzed to preliminarily construct a framework of dispute points in test questions. The study identifies two primary reasons for controversy: (1) inaccuracies in the question information that conflict with factual reality, and (2) the question content delving into areas beyond students' knowledge base. 'Inaccuracies in question information' can be further subdivided into: (a) discrepancies in scenario settings, (b) inconsistencies in answer keys for subjective questions, and (c) oversimplification of geographical processes leading to factual inconsistencies. Consequently, secondary school geography teaching should clarify the evaluative goals of the Gaokao, carefully select contextual content, optimize teaching processes and assessments, thereby cultivating students' thinking abilities and innovative spirit, and promoting the development of geographical core competencies.

Keywords: Chinese social media; disputed geography test questions; secondary school geography education and teaching

1. Introduction

In 2014, the State Council of China launched the reform of the new Gaokao system, placing the study of geography test questions under increased scrutiny (Sun & Yao, 2024). Based on 83 videos discussing controversial test questions from a Chinese social media platform, this study employs qualitative analysis to explore the disputed knowledge points, question formats, and divergent factors within Gaokao geography examinations. The aim is to optimize both test design and teaching pedagogy, serving geography education research within the context of the new Gaokao reform.

Scholars globally recognize the significance of geography education and its assessment. Relevant research primarily focuses on quality assessment in geography education, students' learning and cognitive challenges, and the influence of socio-cultural factors. As a crucial evaluation method, Gaokao geography test questions are a rich subject of domestic research, while international studies are relatively scarce due to differences in subject structures. Lu (2010), analyzing Gaokao simulation questions, revealed issues of rigid thinking and metaphysical errors stemming from an overemphasis on rote memorization in teaching and a neglect of specific contextual analysis in question design. Chen (2014) pointed out that questions concerning Earth's movement should avoid excessive interdisciplinary demands, high cognitive load requirements, and imprecise wording. Feng (2016) emphasized the need for test questions to connect

with the real geographical world to promote knowledge application. Qiu (2018), based on controversies surrounding competency-based conception questions, proposed that design should include detailed materials, standardized charts, authentic contexts, and alignment with academic conditions. Zheng et al. (2022), through analysis of flood-related Gaokao questions and subsequent field exploration, revealed and corrected factual errors reflected in the test questions. In summary, the root causes of disputes over geography test questions involve updates to knowledge systems, demands for competency-based education, and scientific design principles. Future efforts need to focus on conceptual updates and balancing disciplinary depth with competency cultivation.

To further explore these issues, this research follows the process of 'text organization - coding classification - system construction'. First, the video content was systematically transcribed into text. Subsequently, qualitative analysis methods were primarily used for in-depth coding and thematic classification, leading to the preliminary construction of a framework for controversial points in Gaokao geography test questions. During the research process, systematic searches of core Chinese and English databases and library resources, along with intensive reading of literature on Gaokao questions, dispute analysis, qualitative methods, and the new Gaokao reform, provided solid theoretical support for the subsequent analysis. The core of qualitative analysis lies in the inductive interpretation of multimodal data (text, audio, video). This study involved in-depth analysis of sample content, extraction of controversial topics and keywords, identification of core issues, classification of dispute themes, and finally, refinement of key influencing factors and educational implications.

Unlike traditional research focusing on classroom/test structure and difficulty, this study pioneers the systematic examination of Gaokao geography test question discussions on emerging online platforms. Through in-depth analysis of social media videos, particularly the combination of video content and interactive feedback, it not only reveals the unique characteristics and underlying mechanisms of dispute presentation in the digital context but also achieves a comprehensive excavation and understanding of the multiple reasons for controversy generated by test questions.

2. Method

Research Approach and Methodology for Controversial Points in Gaokao Questions

This study adopts a bottom-up inductive logic, following the process of 'text organization - coding classification - system construction'. Specifically:

Text Organization Stage: Videos from a Chinese social media platform served as the research objects. A total of 83 videos posted between March 2018 and January 2024, specifically addressing disputed Gaokao geography test questions, were selected. These were transcribed into text and analyzed as the final sample. During organization, focus was placed on: the controversial points mentioned in the video analyses of disputed questions, the knowledge points examined by the question designers, students' cognitive misunderstandings, and the supporting evidence presented. The textual data was compiled into Table 1 and imported into NVivo software for processing.

Coding Stage: Within NVivo, a series of coding methods were employed, including open coding, axial coding, and selective coding. The codes were systematically merged and classified.

Through this coding process, the controversial points in Gaokao geography test questions were preliminarily constructed, laying a solid foundation for subsequent in-depth analysis.

Table 1 Examples of Video Text Organization Involving Gaokao Geography Disputes

Video Title	Video Presentation Content	Controversial Point Category	Corresponding Test Question
2023 Gaokao National Vol. A, Q6: Freshwater or Saltwater Lake? Plot Twist!	According to the title description, Google Earth shows four lake locations (1,2,3,4). Found: 1 has solar panels, 2 & 3 are farmland, 4 is wasteland. The 'lake' described in the title does not match these observations.	Scenario setting inconsistent with facts	2023 Gaokao National Vol. A, Q6
2017 Beijing Vol. Q36(3): Shorter Freezing Period? Folk Science vs. Official Answer!	Ice flood, ice jam, and other data for the Hungarian section of the Danube prove the freezing period at B is relatively short. However, spring warming starts earlier upstream than midstream, so B's freezing period is actually longer than A's.	Scenario setting inconsistent with facts	2017 Beijing Vol. Q36(3)
Beijing Gaokao Geography Wrong Answers Collection (2012-2023) - Ship Scrapping	Ship scraps come from other countries, not primarily from Chittagong itself. Therefore, proximity to the port is not the main condition. Shipbreaking is divided into dock and beach methods. Chittagong uses beach breaking, making a suitable beach the key condition.	Answer to subjective question inconsistent with facts	2020 Beijing Vol. Q17(2)
Beijing Gaokao Geography Wrong Answers Collection (2012-2023) - Lake Enriquillo	Since 2004, the lake level has risen continuously, flooding villages. A major threat is salinity increase during the rainy season due to freshwater diversion for agriculture. The title oversimplifies the process, leading to factual inconsistency.	Oversimplification of geographical process inconsistent with facts	2018 Beijing Vol. Q36(3) (Implied - context matches)
Beijing Gaokao Geography Wrong Answers Collection (2012-2023) - Soil Organic Matter	High school textbooks do not detail which land type (cultivated, woodland, vegetable) has higher organic matter content. If the cultivated land shown is paddy field, its OM might be higher than some vegetable fields. Soil OM requires specific analysis; the question involves a knowledge blind spot.	Question content involves students' knowledge blind spots	2022 Beijing Vol. Q9

Controversial Points in Gaokao Questions

Through open coding, axial coding, and selective coding of 83 original reference points, this study preliminarily constructed the framework of controversial points for Gaokao geography test questions, as shown in Table 2.

Table 2 Framework of Controversial Points in Gaokao Geography Questions

Dispute Classification	Key Problem	Related Gaokao Questions	Analysis of Controversial Points	Video Title Example
Inaccuracies in Question Information (Conflict with Facts)	Scenario Setting Inconsistent with Facts	2023 National Vol. A, Q6-8	Satellite imagery reveals the four 'lakes' in the area are actually land (solar panels, farmland, wasteland), with no lake water, contradicting the scenario described in the question.	In 2023, does the sixth question of the national Gaokao geography multiple choice question choose fresh water lake or salt water lake? The plot has a reversal
		2017 Beijing Vol. Q36(3)	Research papers indicate River Section A (Komárom to Budapest) has an ice period of ~27 days, while Section B (including Mohács) has ~33 days. The answer key's claim that Section B has a shorter freezing period due to lower latitude is factually incorrect; local scale factors override the broad latitudinal trend.	In 2017, will the freezing period of the Danube River in Beijing be shorter than that in the first place? The folk science flying fox who can't reach the table once again hits the table with the answer only to load the expert's geography official teacher.
	Answer to Subjective Question Inconsistent with Facts	2020 Beijing Vol. Q17(2)	The answer key's "close to the port" lacks scientific basis. Chittagong's beach shipbreaking requires specific tidal, seabed, and slope conditions on suitable beaches, not merely port proximity. Labor, environmental regulations, and markets are key socio-economic factors. The materials provided are insufficient to infer "close to port" as the main condition.	Beijing college entrance examination geography wrong questions collection (2012-2023) year by year wrong, year by year wrong, this is the level of college entrance examination questions. (Ship Scrapping)
		2018 National Vol. 3,	Several factual errors in the answer key: (1) Sua Pan has a railway line (not inconvenient	2018 national college entrance examination geography question-

Dispute Classification	Key Problem	Related Gaokao Questions	Analysis of Controversial Points	Video Title Example
		Q36(2)(3)	transport); (2) The plant involves Anglo American investment (technical level not necessarily 'low'); (3) Freight costs to neighboring South Africa are not necessarily 'high' compared to alternatives; (4) The plant is a JV, not solely a state-owned enterprise.	Botswana soda ash factory joke
	Oversimplification of Geographical Process Inconsistent with Facts	2018 Beijing Vol. Q36(3) (Lake)	The complex interplay of water level and salinity in Lake Enriquillo cannot be attributed solely to climate. The lake level has risen significantly since 2004 due to poorly understood factors, flooding villages. Linking changes simplistically to climate constructs an unrealistic model.	Beijing college entrance examination geography wrong questions collection (2012-2023) year by year wrong, year by year wrong, this is the level of college entrance examination questions. (Lake Enriquillo)
Question Content Involves Students' Knowledge Blind Spots	Knowledge Blind Spot	2023 Hubei Vol. Q13	The difference between options A and D relates to the vertical temperature lapse rate. Students lack the data to know specific air pressure values at given altitudes. Analyzing which city corresponds to the four-month average pressure status is unrealistic without reference data.	In 2023, why the atmospheric pressure in Hubei Province is greater in summer than in winter - A deep interpretation of snow mountain flying fox
		2023 Beijing Vol. Q17(1)	The climate characteristics of Nassau are not covered in standard high school or university textbooks. Its classification (subtropical? tropical savanna?) is itself debated, making it impossible for students to definitively answer.	Beijing college entrance examination geography wrong questions collection (2012-2023) year by year wrong, year by year wrong, this is the level of college entrance examination questions. (Nassau Climate)

Dispute Classification	Key Problem	Related Gaokao Questions	Analysis of Controversial Points	Video Title Example
		2022 Beijing Vol. Q9	High school textbooks do not detail the comparative organic matter content of different land uses (cultivated, forest, vegetable). Soil OM content varies significantly by specific location and type (e.g., paddy vs. dry field, facility vs. open vegetable). The question assumes universal knowledge students don't possess.	In the 2022 college entrance examination geography Beijing volume, there is a garbage question- the ninth question of the multiple choice question. The soil organic matter content of the vegetable land is higher than that of the cultivated land. What is your conclusion based on?
		2022 National Vol. A, Q9-11	The question provides no description or image of the 'Hanggin Banner Grassland' landscape. Students can only speculate based on the name.	In 2022, the national volume A- Hanggai grassland, such college entrance examination geography questions can select talents?
		2020 Beijing Vol. Q17(1)	The 'floating vegetable garden' landscape is not covered in the high school geography curriculum, and no landscape map is provided. Students must rely solely on the brief textual description.	Beijing college entrance examination geography wrong questions collection (2012-2023) year by year wrong, year by year wrong, this is the level of college entrance examination questions. (Floating Garden)
		2020 Beijing Vol. Q17 (Ship)	The question does not explain the shipbreaking process (beach method), leaving students unaware of the specific conditions required for the industry's location.	Beijing college entrance examination geography wrong questions collection (2012-2023) year by year wrong, year by year wrong, this is the level of college entrance examination questions. (Jidagang Shipbreaking)

3. Results

Inaccuracies in Textual Information (Conflict with Facts)

Analysis of the 83 videos reveals that in most controversial questions, designers simplified geographical processes to make the questions suitable for high school students to read, think about, and answer. However, when geographical processes are artificially oversimplified, the geographical entities, phenomena, and their spatiotemporal dynamics become somewhat 'distorted', resulting in the controversial point of 'inconsistency with facts'.

Scenario Setting Inconsistent with Facts.

[Case 1 - 2023 National Vol. A, Q6] Presents a map of a river system on the northern Mediterranean shore, requiring speculation on lake types and water output methods.

Satellite imagery of the given location (38°6'2.28"N, 23°16'10.05"E) shows the four 'lakes' are actually land (site 1: solar panels, sites 2 & 3: farmland, site 4: wasteland), with no lake water, contradicting the scenario described.

Verification shows the question originates from a 2002 SCI journal article. Research in the paper confirms answers to Q7 & Q8: the valley is a former south-draining course; the MN line is an active fault causing basin formation. The author defines sites 1-4 hydrologically/geomorphologically (karst funnels), not as landscape lakes. The 'river flowing into the lake' is a seasonal stream filling these funnels with sediment during rains, enabling agriculture. The scenario set by the test question is thus inconsistent with reality.

[Case 2 - 2017 Beijing Vol. Q36(3)] Provides locations of Hungarian Danube reaches A and B, requiring comparison of hydrological characteristics (B vs A) and causes.

The reference answer assumes lower latitude at B means a shorter freezing period. Research papers show Reach A (~Komárom-Budapest) has an ice period of ~27 days, Reach B (including Mohács) ~33 days (Brill, 2010). Therefore, the answer's claim "Reach B has a shorter freezing period" is incorrect. While large-scale patterns (latitude) influence small-scale phenomena, not all small-scale phenomena perfectly reflect the large-scale trend. The latitude-freezing period correlation holds broadly but does not universally apply at finer scales within the Danube basin.

Answer Keys for Subjective Questions Inconsistent with Facts.

[Case 3 - 2020 Beijing Vol. Q17(2)] Provides a map of Chittagong and information about shipbreaking, asking for the main conditions forming the industry cluster and its environmental problems.

The reference answer lists "'close to the port'" as a condition. However, shipbreaking involves beach and dock methods. Chittagong's beach method requires specific natural conditions: a large tidal range for beaching ships, a firm seabed for stability at low tide, and a gentle beach slope. This method avoids costly infrastructure (Gan, 2009). Key socio-economic factors include abundant cheap labor, lax environmental regulations, and a robust second-hand market. The process involves buying ships internationally, beaching them, stripping materials, and cutting them up (Chen, 2015).

The answer's "close to the port, many scrapped ships, wide sources" lacks scientific basis. Ships are sourced globally via intermediaries. The primary condition is suitable beaches (shipbreaking sites). The question material is insufficient

to infer this, making the answer factually incorrect and tapping into a knowledge blind spot (shipbreaking processes not covered in HS curriculum). Could designers provide scene pictures or process descriptions to scaffold student understanding and align with their zone of proximal development?

[Case 4 - 2018 National Vol. 3, Q36(2)(3)] Presents data on Botswana's Sua Pan Soda Ash plant (steps, sales, losses) and a map, asking for: (2) favorable/unfavorable socio-economic conditions for plant construction, (3) whether the plant should close and why.

Reference answer omissions/errors: (1) Claims "inconvenient transport": Incorrect; Botswana built a 170+ km railway to the plant and salt pans in 1995 (Tan, 1995). (2) Claims "low technical level": Incorrect; the plant was established in 1988 by the Botswana government with Anglo American Corp., De Beers, and AECI (Zhang, 2014). Anglo American involvement contradicts 'low technical level'. (3) Agrees closure due to "high freight": Misleading; primary market is neighboring South Africa. Freight costs would be higher sourcing soda ash from the US, Turkey, or India (Zhang, 2017). (4) Opposes closure to "protect state enterprise": Incorrect; the plant is a joint venture, not a state-owned enterprise as defined by Yan(2021) (citizen-controlled, serving national interests).

Oversimplification of Geographical Processes Inconsistent with Facts.

[Case 5 - 2018 Beijing Vol. Q36(3) - Lake Enriquillo] Provides the lake's location, climate chart (calling it saline), and asks to analyze climate's influence on seasonal water level and salinity changes.

The question simplistically links climate directly to water level changes, aiming to test students' comprehensive thinking about interconnected geographical processes. However, the actual factors influencing Lake Enriquillo's water level are highly complex. Research shows an unprecedented rise of ~17 meters between 2000-2013, flooding farms and villages, with causes not fully understood academically(Rafael et al., 2016). Simplistically attributing changes to climate constructs an unrealistic 'Utopian' model for students to answer.

Question Content Involves Students' Knowledge Blind Spots

Gaokao questions emphasize creating contexts blending production, life, and academia. However, when concepts within these contexts fall outside the high school geography curriculum, appropriate graphic materials should be provided as supplements.

[Case 6 - 2022 Beijing Vol. Q9] Presents a land use map of a hilly area in Shandong Province, asking students to identify the land use type with the highest soil surface organic matter content.

This question creates a land use scenario. Students must judge soil organic matter (SOM) content under different land uses (cultivated, vegetable land), focusing on agricultural development. However, no data on typical SOM levels for different land uses is provided. Research shows SOM content is highly site-specific, lacking universal rules (Alia et al., 2022; Hu et al., 2006; Liu et al., 2017; Zeng et al., 2009). For example, patterns differ between Shouguang (facility ag > open veg > grain), cinnamon soil regions (veg > grain), Sichuan hills (paddy > veg > dryland), and Aksu (intercrop > orchard > field > waste). There's no definitive evidence proving vegetable land (C) has higher SOM than cultivated land (D); if D is paddy field, its SOM might exceed C's. This content represents a significant knowledge blind spot for students.

Similar issues exist in other questions:

2023 Hubei Vol. Q13: Requires understanding vertical temperature lapse rates and calculating air pressure without reference data.

2023 Beijing Vol. Q17(1): Asks about Nassau's climate, which is not covered in textbooks and is itself academically debated.

2020 Beijing Vol. Q17(1): Asks for natural causes of 'floating vegetable gardens' without describing or depicting this landscape (a knowledge blind spot).

2022 National Vol. A, Q9-11 ("Hanggin Banner Grassland"), 2020 Beijing Vol. Q17 ("Chittagong Shipbreaking"): Fail to provide necessary landscape photos or clear conceptual/quantitative descriptions of unfamiliar geographical features or processes not covered in the curriculum.

4. Conclusion

Analysis of the classic and verifiable disputed Gaokao geography questions described in the 83 Chinese social media videos reveals that frequently controversial questions fall into two main categories:

Inaccuracies in Question Information (Conflict with Facts)

Scenarios provided by designers may not match reality, involve 'fictional' geographical elements, oversimplify complex processes, or 'mechanically' apply large-scale laws to smaller scales. This category includes: Scenario setting inconsistencies (e.g., 2023 National Vol. A Q6 'lakes' are farmland/wasteland; 2017 Beijing Vol. Q36(3) Danube freezing period error). Answer key inconsistencies for subjective questions (e.g., 2020 Beijing Vol. Q17(2) shipbreaking conditions; 2018 National Vol. 3 Q36(2)(3) Sua Pan Soda Ash plant details). Oversimplification of geographical processes (e.g., 2018 Beijing Vol. Q36(3) Lake Enriquillo water level linked simplistically to climate).

Question Content Involving Students' Knowledge Blind Spots.

The Gaokao increasingly follows a 'no context, no question' trend. As contexts become more complex, questions risk exceeding students' knowledge base if unfamiliar geographical features/processes (e.g., Nassau's climate 2023, Hanggin Grassland 2022, soil OM variation 2022, shipbreaking/floating gardens 2020) are introduced without adequate supporting materials or curriculum coverage. Students cannot reliably answer through 'imagination' alone, hindering the assessment of geographical thinking and core competencies.

Clarify the Goal Orientation of Gaokao Geography Assessment.

The core of Gaokao geography assessment should extend beyond simple knowledge recall to evaluate creative thinking. The new Gaokao reform aims to promote deep learning and cultivate geographical core competencies. Therefore, question designers should: Anchor question design in fundamental educational goals, focusing tightly on cultivating core competencies. Fully consider the realities of geography teaching, avoiding disconnects between test content and curriculum or overly tangential themes, ensuring test validity and relevance.

Learn from International Practices: Japan: Rigorous, closed-form multiple-choice questions minimize subjective vocabulary, using real geographical phenomena as context to enhance validity. UK A-Level: Employs open-ended questions without fixed answers, emphasizing authentic geographical scenarios and landscape maps. This stimulates

divergent thinking, requiring students to apply principles to explain real events, enhancing logical thinking and practical geographical skills.

Select Appropriate Contextual Content

Controversies often arise from oversimplified contexts or answer keys overly tailored to existing knowledge frameworks, perceived as lacking depth or disciplinary rigor. To counter this: Focus on showcasing the holistic relationships and spatiotemporal evolution of geographical elements within contexts. This guides students to analyze interactions at scales reflecting real-world complexity. Require students to extract multiple problem-solving conditions from the context, forming coherent solution pathways. This enhances the discipline's rigor and better assesses core competencies and problem-solving skills (Zhu et al., 2023). Ensure Scientific Rigor and Support: Recognize geography's inherent complexity (spanning natural/human geography, space, time, human activity). Designers should: Source contextual materials primarily from recent papers in authoritative academic journals. Conduct field verification or consult domain experts (e.g., for shipbreaking conditions, lake hydrology) to guarantee the scientific validity, authority, and timeliness of contextual materials. Frame answers to emphasize assessing students' geographical knowledge reserves and information processing skills, minimizing potential gaps between academic research and secondary school knowledge (Zhu et al., 2023). In Teaching: Teachers should fully demonstrate geography's rich connotations and multiple perspectives, guiding comprehensive understanding, and prioritize cultivating thinking ability and innovative spirit.

Emphasize Secondary School Geography Teaching Processes and Assessment

Maintain Relevance: Geography is intrinsically linked to real life. Teaching content must be updated to reflect contemporary geographical phenomena, trends, and hot topics. Guide students to observe local geographical issues, fostering practical skills and social responsibility. Reform Assessment: Move beyond scores as the sole metric. Implement process-oriented and comprehensive evaluations, respecting individual differences and promoting holistic development. Deepen Teacher Engagement: Teachers must deeply explore the new Gaokao's question formats and assessment methods. Pedagogically, focus on: How to guide students in transforming knowledge into practical application skills to handle complex, integrated examinations. Deconstructing teaching objectives and problems meticulously for targeted solutions. Supplementing instruction with real geographical process case studies (e.g., Lake Enriquillo hydrology) to avoid the pitfalls of oversimplified models. Continuously innovating teaching methods to scientifically build a teaching system aligned with the new Gaokao evaluation framework (Guo, 2023).

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